

A spray volume calculation chart for 19-, 16-, and 10-liter capacity knapsack sprayers

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Spraying is the most common method Asian rice farmers use to apply insecticides. Knapsack sprayers with 19-, 16-, or 10-liter capacities are popular. Good insect control can be achieved with contact or stomach poisons if rice foliage is covered by the spray solution. Spraying rice is time-consuming and laborious, and requires much water. In irrigated rice areas, water is usually available in the rice field or from nearby canals. But in rainfed areas, a water source may be far away, and refilling may require many trips. Dosage calculations have been based on 1,000-liters/ha, a spray volume often stipulated in insecticide recommendations. Recent IRRI studies, however, have shown that the stipulated amount is unrealistically high. For each application, farmers spraying 1 ha would have to refill their 19-, 16-, and 10-liter sprayers 53, 63, and 100 times, respectively. Farmers rarely do that and it is unnecessary. For example, excellent brown planthopper control can be achieved at booting with perthane sprayed at the low volume of 190 liters/ha. But for safety, farmers are advised to apply 300–500 liters/ha to further dilute the insecticide spray. Low spray volumes (300 liters/ha) are adequate when rice plants are small (before maximum tillering) but volumes must be higher (500 liters/ha) when the rice canopy has closed. Spray-volume calculation requires knowledge of the field area, sprayer capacity, and number of sprayerloads per field. Farmers generally possess such knowledge and a chart has been developed for use by extension workers in helping farmers improve their proficiency in insecticide application. The following formula is used to determine the spray volume in liters per hectare:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{No. of sprayerloads)} \\ \text{per field x sprayer capacity (liters)} \end{array} \quad \times \quad \frac{1}{\text{area of field (ha)}}$$

To use the chart, first determine the size of the sprayer and refer to that section designated 19-, 16, and 10-liter capacity. To find the spray volume for 0.1- to 2.5-ha fields, refer to the column heads designating the area of the field in hectares. Along the left margin is the number of sprayerloads per field, from 5 to 50 in increments of 5. You may need to round off. Follow the appropriate row for sprayer size and column for field area to find the spray volume. For example:

- With a 19-liter sprayer and a 1.4-ha field, 30 sprayerloads/field will apply 407 liters/ha;
- With a 10-liter sprayer and a 0.8-ha field, 10 sprayer-loads/field will apply 125 liters/ha. In this case, the farmer should increase his spray volume to 20 or 25 sprayerloads/ha and apply 250 to 313 liters/ha.

Calculation of spray volume for knapsack sprayers of 19-liter (5-US gallon), 16-liter (4.2-US gallon), and 10-liter (2.6-US gallon) capacities. IRRI, 1980.

Sprayerloads (no./field)	Spray volume (liters/ha) when field size is											
	0.2 ha	0.4 ha	0.6 ha	0.8 ha	1.0 ha	1.2 ha	1.4 ha	1.6 ha	1.8 ha	2.0 ha	2.2 ha	2.4 ha
<i>19-liter capacity backpack sprayer</i>												
5	475	238	158	119	95	79	68	59	53	48	43	40
10	950	475	317	238	190	158	136	119	106	95	86	79
15	1425	713	475	356	285	238	204	178	158	143	130	119
20	1900	950	633	475	380	317	271	238	211	190	173	158
25	2375	1188	792	594	475	396	339	297	264	238	216	198
30	2850	1425	950	713	570	475	407	356	317	285	259	238
35	3325	1663	1108	831	665	554	475	417	369	333	302	277
40	3800	1900	1267	950	760	633	543	475	422	380	345	317
45	4275	2138	1425	1069	855	713	641	534	475	428	389	356
50	4750	2375	1583	1188	950	792	679	594	528	475	434	396
<i>16-liter capacity backpack sprayer</i>												
5	400	200	133	100	80	67	57	50	44	40	36	33
10	800	400	267	200	160	133	114	100	89	80	73	67
15	1200	600	400	300	240	200	171	150	133	120	109	100
20	1600	800	534	400	320	267	229	200	178	160	145	133
25	2000	1000	667	500	400	333	286	250	222	200	182	167
30	2400	1200	800	600	480	400	343	300	267	240	218	200
35	2800	1400	934	700	560	466	400	350	311	280	255	233
40	3200	1600	1067	800	640	533	457	400	356	320	291	267
45	3600	1800	1200	900	720	600	514	450	400	360	327	300
50	4000	2000	1334	1000	800	667	571	500	444	400	364	333
<i>10-liter capacity backpack sprayer</i>												
5	250	120	83	63	50	42	36	31	28	25	23	21
10	500	250	167	125	100	83	71	63	56	50	45	42
15	750	375	250	188	150	125	107	94	83	75	68	63
20	1000	500	333	250	200	167	143	125	111	100	91	83
25	1250	625	417	313	250	208	179	156	139	125	114	104
30	1500	750	500	375	300	250	214	188	167	150	136	125
35	1750	875	583	438	350	292	250	219	194	175	159	146
40	2000	1000	667	500	400	333	286	250	222	200	182	167
45	2250	1125	750	563	450	375	321	281	250	225	205	188
50	2500	1250	833	625	500	417	357	313	278	250	227	208